

EVALUATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND TEST PROCEDURE FOR

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

R. R. Hart
Bell Laboratories
Murray Hill, New Jersey 07974

Almost all mechanical properties of composites are determined from tension tests. Fracture toughness properties are possibly the main exception. Since most of these composites are stressed in bending, many times bend tests provide the required information directly. A bend test and procedure is described that is well suited for evaluating composite materials in strip form. The test is based on the dynamic determination of energy dissipation in a specimen stressed in bending. Stiffness values, the maximum permissible deformations within a specified offset yield strain and the minimum radius of curvatures are determined. Cyclic behavior and the dependency of these properties on orientation, temperature and cold work are shown. Reproducibility of test results and equipment calibration are also shown. The significance of the results are discussed and compared with conventional tension tests. An example is shown which illustrates the operation of the test and the calculation of results.

Introduction

To take full advantage of the attractive features offered by many metallic composites more information is required of their mechanical properties - especially those properties within or near the elastic limit. Much of the work shown in the literature on composite testing reports mechanical properties derived from tension tests. Namely tensile strength, yield strength at 0.2% offset and elongation, all of which are far into the plastic range where many members will cease to function. The notable exceptions are a few fracture toughness tests in bending and impact studies.

Since few structural members are exposed only to tensile stresses, mechanical properties from tensile tests may be inadequate to characterize materials. This is especially true for composite laminates used in a bending mode where the member is stressed in a fashion that have little in common with tensile properties.

The purpose of this paper is to report the findings of bend tests made on composite laminate strip and to illustrate the test procedure used to determine their properties.

Equipment

The composite material in strip form was tested using the WT-Bend Tester.¹ The principle behind the test is that energy dissipated during plastic deformation is large. For most materials, deformation within the elastic range is nearly reversible, i.e. most of the energy required for deformation can be recovered. At the beginning of plastic deformation, energy dissipation within the material increases drastically. The WT-bend test is set up so that a fixed amount of energy is supplied to a vibrating specimen during each half cycle. As a result of this added energy, the amplitude of the vibrating specimen increases until steady state is reached. At this point, the energy supplied to the specimen equals the energy dissipated by it. The steady state amplitude and the frequency of oscillation of the specimen is then determined directly from the tester. The elastic modulus is calculated from the frequency and specimen dimensions, and the design stress or strain may be calculated from the steady state amplitude. Since the frequencies of oscillation are low, < 5 Hz, air friction is negligible. Therefore, the only losses which influences the pendulum's motion are jaw friction and the energy dissipated within the specimen itself. Effects of jaw friction are substantially reduced by maintaining a specimen length to thickness ratio ≥ 25 . Calibration of the tester involves determining the mass moment of inertia of the pendulum and the procedure used to accomplish this is given in the appendix.

During test, energy is supplied to the system by a forced displacement of the table T which rotates the lower jaw through an

angle equivalent to $\Delta\Phi$, Fig. 1. This causes a decrease in the specimen's curvature and results in an increase in the stored energy. As a consequence, the energy added is determined by the magnitude of $\Delta\Phi$ and the pendulum's amplitude Φ_a .

$$W = 2C\Phi_a\Delta\Phi = 2J\omega^2\Phi_a\Delta\Phi \quad (1)$$

where; W is the work per cycle, C is the spring constant, J is the mass moment of the pendulum about the center of the gage length. In steady state, the energy supplied to the specimen is equal to the energy dissipated by the specimen. The frequency of the oscillating pendulum is measured electrically and may be used to establish the modulus. For flat, rectangular specimens the modulus is obtained from;

$$E = \frac{48\pi^2 J \ell f^2}{bh^3} \quad (2)$$

where b , h , ℓ are width, thickness and length of the specimen, and f is the frequency of the pendulum.

To distinguish between results from the bend test and the offset yield strength normally obtained from tension data, an allowable stress is used and called the design stress. It is the stress developed in the specimen resulting from the vibrating pendulum when subjected to some value of $\Delta\Phi$. In the analysis by Weissmann,² the factor .87 is applied to account for the strain distribution in bending. For a rectangular specimen the design stress is expressed as:

$$\sigma = \frac{3.6Jf^2\Phi_a}{bh^2} \quad (3)$$

where, Φ_a is the angle of pendulum rotation and J is the mass moment of inertia of the pendulum.

Equation 2 and 3 only hold true for a monolithic material. Although the strain is known, stress values are not, because the modulus and elastic limits of the composite constituents are different. Mechanical properties of the laminate composites investigated are shown as strain amplitude ϵ_a at some offset strain $\Delta\epsilon$, and a stiffness per unit width. Where monolithic materials are used to illustrate the reproducibility of test results, Eqs. 2 and 3 are employed.

Test Procedure

Generally, any thin flat metallic material can be tested using this bend tester. With the present apparatus thicknesses from ~ 0.005 in. (0.127 mm) to ~ 0.030 in. (0.762 mm) can be tested.

Rectangular specimens about 0.50 in. (12 mm) wide by 2 in. (52 mm) long are sheared from stock. The thickness, h and width, b are measured and the specimen is clamped between the pendulum and table jaws. A spacer is used to conveniently fix the gage length, ℓ . The pendulum, now entirely supported by the specimen, is set in motion and when a steady state condition is reached the frequency of oscillation and the pendulum's angular amplitude Φ_a is read from the test unit.

An example is used to illustrate the procedure. The specimen was cut from a 3 layer sheet of laminate composite; two layers of 5% thickness of copper over 1045 carbon steel. The composite previously cold rolled to 60% thickness reduction, was tested with the long dimension of the specimen transverse to the rolling direction. The material was stress relieved 2 hours at 185°C and tested at 173°C. The dimensions are:

thickness, $h = 0.0101$ in. (0.256 mm)

width, $w = 0.6093$ in. (15.476 mm)

gage length spacer, $\ell = 0.750$ in. (19.050 mm)

An offset strain $\Delta\epsilon$ equal to 1.35×10^{-5} was chosen for this test, since this value is within the elastic range. To accomplish this value, the solenoids s (Fig. 1) are adjusted to rotate the table through an angle $\Delta\Phi$ of 0.155 degrees, i.e.

$$\Delta\Phi = \frac{2\ell\Delta\epsilon}{h} = \frac{2(0.75 \text{ in.})(1.35 \times 10^{-5}) \text{ rad.}}{0.010 \text{ in.}} \times \frac{57.3^\circ}{\text{rad}} = 0.115^\circ$$

The vertical movement of the solenoids necessary for a rotation of 0.115° is 0.010 in. (0.25 mm). The pendulum P is then set in motion. Its amplitude Φ_a will gradually increase until the system reaches equilibrium. At equilibrium Φ_a was found to be 7.75° and the frequency of the pendulum is 1.85 Hz.

Since equations 2 and 3 can not be used for laminates, strain amplitude ϵ_a at a specified offset strain $\Delta\epsilon$ is shown in Figs. 2-5. The strain amplitude is equal to;

$$\epsilon_a = \frac{\Phi_a h}{2\ell} \quad (4)$$

The offset strain $\Delta\epsilon$ (bending) is approximately equal to the offset strain determined in tension. $\Delta\epsilon$ is adjustable to a desired value by adjusting the solenoid rods. ϵ_a is then the maximum total strain experienced by the specimen and depends on the material properties and the setting of $\Delta\epsilon$.

Composite laminates consisting of either a 5 or 10% copper (OFHC) layer on each side of a 1045 medium carbon steel were studied in a range of cold reductions from 0 to 60%. Copper and steel strips with 70% cold reduction of the same material used to fabricate the composites were also tested.

Test Results

Initially, bend tests were conducted to determine the variation in mechanical properties with cold working. These tests were conducted with $\Delta\epsilon = 0.0001$ which closely approximates the 0.01% offset yield strain in tension. The resulting ϵ_a vs. percent reduction of the 316 composite (5% copper layers) is shown in Fig. 2. Increasing cold work increases ϵ_a by about 170%. The transverse direction is stiffer than the rolling direction and has a higher ϵ_a as well. Similar trends were also observed in composite 326. A comparison of the differences of the two composites are shown in Fig. 3 where the effect of the thickness of the copper layers can be seen. The thicker copper layer shows a lower ϵ_a . The relationship of ϵ_a to $\Delta\epsilon$ was next determined. The test sequence involves setting $\Delta\epsilon$ to some low value ≈ 0.000013 and establishing the corresponding ϵ_a . $\Delta\epsilon$ is then increased and a new ϵ_a obtained. This procedure continues until $\Delta\epsilon = .0001$. This relation is shown in Fig. 4, where $\Delta\epsilon$ to ϵ_a is seen to be linear to about $\Delta\epsilon$ of 0.00004. The vertical lines in Figs. 4 and 5 correspond to $\Delta\epsilon = 0.0001$.

The effects of prior cycling on ϵ_a vs. $\Delta\epsilon$ was also investigated. To do this, a specimen is tested at a small $\Delta\epsilon$ of about .00001 and the ϵ_a is recorded. The test is allowed to continue at this level to determine whether ϵ_a decreases. If not, $\Delta\epsilon$ was increased and ϵ_a again noted. At some value of $\Delta\epsilon$, ϵ_a decreased as the number of cycles increased. The specimen was allowed to cycle until ϵ_a stabilized. A new untested specimen is then used and the test starts at the next higher $\Delta\epsilon$. Again ϵ_a is observed and cycling is allowed to continue until ϵ_a stops decreasing. This procedure continues to $\Delta\epsilon = .0001$. The results of these data are shown in Fig. 5, where the curves show cyclic changes at various $\Delta\epsilon$ levels and indicates the extent of material change. Also included are unloading curves, i.e. after ϵ_a stabilize, $\Delta\epsilon$ was decreased in several steps. In each case the linear portion of the original curve was decreased indicating the specimen absorbs more energy for the same work input.

Predicting Behavior

Specimens of 1045 steel and OFHC copper, used to make the composites, were rolled to 70% thickness reduction and tested at the 0.01% offset strain (.0001 $\Delta\epsilon$). Using these results together

with strains determined from testing the composite, the maximum stress in the copper layer was calculated to be ~ 23 ksi, the stress in the copper at the interface to be ~ 21 ksi and the maximum stress in the steel to be 42 ksi. Figures 6 and 7 shows the stress in the copper at the 0.01% offset yield to be a little more than 20 ksi. The stress in the steel, at .9 h from the neutral axis, to be 48 ksi. Considering that the component materials were cold worked 70% vs. 60% for the composite, the differences are fairly small. The discrepancies in the calculated and measured values are also influenced by the interfaces of the two metals.

Residual Stresses

The first tests of the composites were done about 15 days after fabrication. Ninety-five days later the same material was again tested. ϵ_a vs. $\Delta\epsilon$ in both orientations were found to be considerably lower, Fig. 9. It is thought that these differences are caused by relaxation of the residual stresses induced during rolling, since the differences were greater in the higher tempers. In the annealed condition, where residual stresses are absent or very low, the time of test after fabrication made almost no difference in the results.

Results at Elevated Temperatures

Composite materials with 10% and 60% cold work were used for temperature studies. The problem of whether decreases in ϵ_a vs. $\Delta\epsilon$ were caused by temperature increase, by cycling or both was handled in the following manner: First, $\Delta\epsilon$ was held to a low value, i.e. less than .000015 where cyclic softening is known to be negligible, see Fig. 4.

A specimen was cycled at some $\Delta\epsilon$ value for approximately 4000 cycles at room temperature to determine changes in ϵ_a vs. number of cycles Figs. 9 and 10. Next a fresh specimen was^a tested at various temperatures noting the corresponding ϵ_a , Figs. 11 and 12. The curves without data points show ϵ_a at room temperature for a corresponding number of cycles at that temperature therefore any differences of ϵ_a between the two curves can be attributed to temperature effects. ϵ_a of material with 10% reduction in the T.D. show no effect up to 100°C, while in the R.D. ϵ_a continues to decrease as the temperature increases. Figure 12 show ϵ_a vs. number of cycles for the 60% C.W. material. The small square data points in Figs. 11 and 12 correspond to values of ϵ_a for material heated to the indicated temperature and then tested^a. In this manner previous cycling at lower temperatures was not experienced by the material. The data verify small changes are due to cycling, but rather are caused by increasing temperatures. These results apply within the 4000 cycles used for this work.

Stiffness of the 316 composite vs. temperature is shown in Fig. 13. In all cases the stiffness is constant vs. the number of cycles at room temperature, but tends to decrease at elevated temperatures. The same is true of composite 326 (not shown).

Design Data

Although the following data³ were not obtained from composite materials, it will nevertheless illustrate one method of using data obtained from the bend test. The appendix show the equations used to calculate the values needed to construct Figs. 14, 15 and 16.

Figure 14 shows the unit stiffness vs. thickness of flat springs made from various copper alloys. Note the small differences in the spring's stiffnesses at a specified thickness. Stiffness vs. thickness does not supply much information as far as what material to use. However, if the permissible moment vs. thickness is used, Fig. 15, the superiority of one material over another becomes apparent. The permissible moment is defined as the maximum moment without exceeding a specified offset strain, in this case $\Delta\epsilon = 0.0001$. Now consider two springs of equal geometry, one made of item A and one of item B. If the springs are compared on the basis of stiffness only, both are about of equal value. For a thickness of 0.009 in. (.225 mm) the stiffnesses are 1.1 and 1.15 lb. in./rad. Now if the springs are operated to the same radius of curvature, (Fig. 16) say 0.91 in. (22.8 mm) item A will operate at 100% of its permissible moment while item B will operate at only 60% of its permissible moment. Stress relaxation, creep, and fatigue can therefore be expected to be less of a problem using the spring made of item B.

The test data obtained from the WT-Bend Test compared with standard tensile test data show significantly better reproducibility. 3:1 improvement in standard deviation for the design stress vs. 0.01% offset tensile yield strength and a 2:1 improvement in the elastic modulus resulted.⁴ Furthermore, in many instances the bend test more closely duplicates actual loading conditions and, provides more realistic data.

Summary

Composite 316 with 10% Cold Work

- a - Both orientations show a decrease in the outside fiber strain amplitude, ϵ_a with increasing number of cycles at room temperature. At $\sim 170^\circ\text{C}$, ϵ_a is constant vs. number of cycles, but significantly lower than at room temperature.
- b - Outside fibre strain amplitude ϵ_a is always about 30% higher in the transverse direction.

- c - Stiffness per unit width in both orientations is constant vs. number of cycles at room temperature, but decreases with increasing temperature.

Composite 316 With 60% Cold Work

- a - Outside fibre strain amplitude ϵ_a , decreases with increasing cycling in the rolling direction but remains constant in the transverse direction.
- b - At elevated temperatures, 165°C to 170°C, ϵ_a in both orientations are constant up to 2000 cycles.
- c - Outside fibre strain amplitude ϵ_a , is higher in the transverse orientation.
- d - Stiffness per unit width in both orientations is constant vs. the number of cycles at room temperature. As temperature increases, the stiffness decreases.

Conclusions

Few of the findings reported here are unexpected, but it illustrates that the test method can be used effectively to establish mechanical properties vs. temperature, offset strains, and number of cycles. The test should be valuable to test sheet in-situ composites where they can be studied as if they were monolithic materials. The temperature range used for these tests are low compared to most composites testing, but little difficulty should be experienced adopting the test unit for the necessary higher temperatures, since none of the electrical apparatus need be exposed to the heat.

The test is well suited to sense differences in percent cold work, orientation and percent differences in composite layers. In addition, cyclic effects and maximum ϵ_a at a specified $\Delta\epsilon$ are readily determined. The maximum permissible moment without exceeding a predetermined offset strain, the relationship between thickness and stiffness, permissible moment, minimum permissible radius of curvature are all easily acquired. Reproducibility of test results of elastic design properties are superior to conventional tensile test methods.⁵

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List of Symbols

- J_1 = mass moment of inertia of pendulum about axis B, in lb.sec.²
 J_0 = mass moment of inertia of fixture about axis B, in lb.sec.²
 m_0 = mass of fixture, grams
 m_1 = mass of pendulum, grams
 d = distance from center of mass to axis A, inch
 ω_0 = angular velocity of fixture about axis A, rad/sec
 ω_1 = angular velocity of fixture and pendulum combined about axis A, rad/sec
 f_0 = frequency of fixture about axis A, Hz
 f_1 = frequency of pendulum about axis A, Hz
 f = frequency of pendulum due to test specimen, Hz
 g = acceleration of gravity, ft/sec²
 l = apparent gage length established by spacer thickness, inch
 l_e = effective gage length of test specimen, inch
 h = specimen thickness, inch
 b = specimen width, inch
 E = modulus of elasticity, lbs/in²
 σ = stress, lbs/in²
 ϵ = offset yield strain
 Φ_a = angular deflection of pendulum, degrees
 ϵ_a = strain amplitude
 $\Delta\epsilon$ = offset strain

Appendix

The calibration procedure used establishes the mass moment of inertia of the pendulum about an axis that corresponds to the center of the specimen's gage length. This is accomplished by clamping a special fixture into the pendulum jaws and balancing

the unit around that axis, see Figure 17. Next, the unit is oscillated about a known distance from the center of mass. The fixture alone was balanced and oscillated in a similar manner before clamping it into the pendulum. With the masses of the pendulum and fixture, together with their frequencies, J of the pendulum can be determined in the following manner:

$$\bar{J}_0 = J_0 + m_0 d^2 \quad (5)$$

where subscript 0 refers to the fixture quantities and d is the distance from the center of mass to the axis of rotation.

The angular frequency of the fixture is $\omega_0 = \frac{m_0 g d}{J_0}$ from which

$$J_0 = \frac{m_0 g d}{\omega_0^2} - m_0 d^2 \quad (6)$$

The angular frequency of the pendulum and fixture acting as a unit is

$$\omega_\mu = \frac{m_0 d g + m_1 d g}{J_0 + J_1 + m_0 d^2 + m_1 d^2}$$

and

$$J_1 = \frac{m_0 g d}{\omega_\mu^2} - \frac{m_1 g d}{\omega_0^2} - m_0 d^2 - m_1 d^2 + J_0 \quad (7)$$

Subscript μ refers to quantities of the pendulum and fixture acting as a unit and subscript 1 refers to the pendulum quantities. Substituting $4\pi^2 f^2$ for ω^2 , W for mg and

$\frac{m_0 g d}{\omega_0^2} - m_0 d^2$ for J_0 , Eq. (7) reduces

$$J_1 = \frac{W_0 d}{4\pi^2} \left[\frac{1}{f_\mu^2} - \frac{1}{f_0^2} \right] + W_1 d \left[\frac{1}{4\pi^2 f_\mu^2} - \frac{d}{g} \right] \quad (8)$$

With J_1 established, the frequency f of the pendulum, caused by a specimen of known modulus, is determined and used in Eq. (1) to find l_e , the effective gage length.

A complete description of the calibration procedure and the significance of the effective l_e is given elsewhere by the author.⁶ The following equations were used to determine:

(1) Bending stiffness per unit width and unit length C_0

$$C_0 = 4\pi^2 f^2 \frac{\ell}{b}$$

- (2) Maximum bending moment per unit width M_0

$$M_0 = 0.87 \frac{C_0}{\ell} \Phi_a$$

- (3) Minimum radius of curvature ρ

$$\rho = 1.15 \frac{\ell}{\Phi_0}$$

- (4) Design strain ϵ_1

$$\epsilon_1 = 0.435 \frac{h}{\ell} \Phi_a$$

- (5) Design stress σ_1

$$\sigma_1 = E\epsilon_1 \left(1 - \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\epsilon_1} \right)$$

- (6) Angle of table rotation $\Delta\Phi$

$$\Delta\Phi = \frac{2\ell_t}{h} \Delta\epsilon$$

where:

f = frequency in Hz

J = mass moment of inertia, in. lbs. sec.²

ℓ = gage length of specimen, inch.

b = width of specimen, inch.

h = thickness of specimen, inch.

Φ_a = amplitude of specimen rotation, radians.

ℓ_t = distance from center of table to solenoid rod, in.

Fig. 1 WT-Bend Tester

Fig. 2 Strain Amplitude and Stiffness vs. Percent Reduction-Composite 316.

Fig. 3 Effect of Copper Thickness on the Strain Amplitude vs. Percent Reduction-Composites 316 and 326.

Fig. 4 Strain Amplitude vs. Offset Strain-Composite 316-60% Reduction - T.D.

Fig. 5 Strain Amplitude vs. Offset Strain as Number of Cycles Increase Composite 316-10% Reduction-R.D.

Fig. 6 Design Stress vs. Offset Strain of 1045 Steel (Composite Constituent) 70% Reduction-R.D.

Fig. 7 Design Stress vs. Offset Strain of OFHC Copper (Composite Constituent) 70% Reduction-R.D.

Fig. 8 Effect of Time after Fabrication of Strain Amplitude vs. Percent Reduction-Composite 316.

Fig. 9 Strain Amplitude vs. Number of Cycles-Composite 316-10% Reduction.

Fig. 10 Strain Amplitude vs. Number of Cycles-Composite 316-60% Reduction.

Fig. 11 Strain Amplitude vs. Temperature-Composite 316-10% Reduction.

Fig. 12 Strain Amplitude vs. Temperature-Composite 316-60% Reduction.

Fig. 13 Stiffness vs. Temperature-Composite 316-60% Reduction.

Fig. 14 Stiffness vs. Thickness of Several Copper Alloy Springs.

Fig. 15 Permissible Moment vs. Thickness of Several Copper Alloy Springs.

Fig. 16 Minimum Radius of Curvature of Several Copper Alloy Springs.

Fig. 17 Calibration of Pendulum Showing Arrangement of Fixture in Pendulum Jaws.